

DEDNAED

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Project Acronym: DeDNAed

Deliverable 8.5

Second version of the exploitation and dissemination plan

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1	13.2.2023	BNN, Caitlin Ahern	1 st draft – all changes from the original deliverable (other than minor grammar and usage) are depicted in green
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The main work on this deliverable report was performed by BNN, leader of WP8 on “Marketing (Dissemination & Exploitation)”. [Caitlin Ahern](#), Nerea Argarate and Susanne Resch, scientific researchers at BNN, developed and coordinate the overall communication and dissemination strategy within the DeDNAed project and researchers from TECNALIA, Nerea Briz and Goran Bijelic, contributed to the Exploitation strategy. Additionally, all project partners contributed input and feedback to the creation of the DeDNAed PDER. [Caitlin Ahern \(BNN\)](#) was responsible for the [M24 Update as Deliverable 8.5](#), and [Julia Hann \(TUC\)](#) reviewed the final version. This PDER report will be updated in M36 as the final version (D8.7).

Abbreviations

No specific abbreviations used.

Executive Summary

The Exploitation and Dissemination Plan aims to present all the key exploitable results generated on the course of the DeDNAed project as well as how the consortium partners can exploit them after the end of the project. The analysis contents to be elaborated for each key exploitable result include exploitable innovations and ambitions, objective of exploitation, exploitation strategy and intellectual property rights management.

In this second version of the Exploitation and Dissemination Plan, the key exploitable results identified previously are reviewed and updated if necessary. This update is based on meetings held with partners and to questionnaires and emails sent by all partners responsible for the exploitation of at least one Key Exploitable Result. As research was conducted and results, as well as challenges, arose during this period, this exploitation plan includes advancements, but also uncertainties regarding the exploitation of some Key Exploitable Results.

It also outlines the communication and dissemination strategy to be followed during the project in order to maximize awareness of the project and its output. The strategy includes the project branding, such as logo, colors and templates, the website, the social media presence. It looks as stakeholders and identifies publications and events of interest, such as conferences, fairs, and public events or educational activities. A log of communication & dissemination activities is contained as an annex.

In this second version, minor updates to the communication & dissemination strategy were made (in green). Of note is the decision to discontinue using Twitter as a social media platform.

Table of Contents

Document History	2
1. Introduction & background	6
Description of the task	6
Project background and objectives	7
Objectives of the first Plan for the Dissemination and Exploitation of Results (PDER)	7
2. Communication and Dissemination activities	8
Communication & Dissemination Strategy	8
Internal Communication	8
External Communication & Dissemination	8
Key Performance Indicators	10
Communication and Dissemination activities during the first year	12
<i>Project Logo</i>	<i>12</i>
<i>Project Website</i>	<i>13</i>
<i>Project Brand Guideline</i>	<i>14</i>
<i>Communication Toolkit & Dissemination Package</i>	<i>14</i>
<i>Social Media in the Project</i>	<i>15</i>
<i>DeDNAed Stakeholders</i>	<i>19</i>
<i>Scientific Publications and events</i>	<i>20</i>
<i>Open Research data</i>	<i>20</i>
<i>Conferences, Fairs, non-scientific and Public events</i>	<i>21</i>
<i>Educational activities, synergies, attendance to funding events and others</i>	<i>22</i>
Monitoring Communication and Dissemination activities	22
Completed Communication & Dissemination Activities	24
3. Exploitation plan	24
Innovation objectives of DeDNAed project	24
A. <i>Exploitable innovations and ambitions</i>	<i>26</i>
B. <i>Objective of exploitation</i>	<i>26</i>
C. <i>Exploitation strategy</i>	<i>26</i>
D. <i>IPR management</i>	<i>26</i>
A. Exploitable innovations and ambitions	26

DEDNAED

KER 1. Cluster decorated, DNA origami compatible DNA based bioRE.....	26
KER 2. Cluster decorated, DNA origami compatible Antibody based bioRE	27
KER 3. DNA origami sensor platform based on SERS detection	28
KER 4. Optimized thin-film system for selective surface immobilisation.....	28
B. Objective of exploitation	29
KER 1. Cluster decorated, DNA origami compatible DNA based bioRE.....	29
KER 2. Cluster decorated, DNA origami compatible Antibody based bioRE	30
KER 3. DNA origami sensor platform based on SERS detection	30
KER 4. Optimized thin-film system for selective surface immobilisation.....	30
C. Exploitation strategy	30
KER 1. Cluster decorated, DNA origami compatible DNA based bioRE.....	31
KER 2. Cluster decorated, DNA origami compatible Antibody based bioRE	31
KER 3. DNA origami sensor platform based on SERS detection	31
KER 4. Optimized thin-film system for selective surface immobilisation.....	32
D. IPR management	32
KER 1. Cluster decorated, DNA origami compatible DNA based bioRE.....	32
KER 2. Cluster decorated, DNA origami compatible Antibody based bioRE	32
KER 3. DNA origami sensor platform based on SERS detection	32
KER 4. Optimized thin-film system for selective surface immobilisation.....	33
4. Conclusions	33
5. References & Bibliography	34
Annexes.....	35
Annex 1. DeDNAed Communication and Dissemination LOG as of 31 December 2022.....	36

1. Introduction & background

Description of the task

The DeDNAed project has been awarded funding by the European Commission (EC), which requires the consortium to communicate the project and disseminate/exploit its results to specific stakeholders and a wider public community. Professional communication, dissemination and exploitation is a key element for successful marketing. Effective dissemination of project outcomes will ensure the use of results and maximize DeDNAed project impact.

Within the DeDNAed work plan, WP8 led by BNN is focussed on “Dissemination & Exploitation”. The aim of WP8 is to ensure a consistent Dissemination & Exploitation of the project’s scientific and technological results, safeguarding optimal visibility and both a European and worldwide outreach to all relevant stakeholders (R&D community, industry, regulatory bodies and general society). Deliverable 8.5 “Plan for Dissemination and Exploitation of Project Results (PDER)” directly serves to achieve the following specific objectives within WP8:

- **O.8.1: Disseminate** all scientific/technological **results** to the scientific, technical and medical **community**
- **O.8.2:** Ensure an ongoing collaboration of the consortium for **successful exploitation** of **innovations** also beyond the project period
- **O.8.3:** Ensure **efficient management** of DeDNAed **project data**

This document shall be understood as supporting means to fulfil all obligations agreed with in the grant agreement, explicitly the Articles listed below:

Article 26 — OWNERSHIP OF RESULTS

Article 27 — PROTECTION OF RESULTS — VISIBILITY OF EU FUNDING

Article 28 — EXPLOITATION OF RESULTS

Article 29 — DISSEMINATION OF RESULTS — OPEN ACCESS — VISIBILITY OF EU FUNDING

Article 30 — TRANSFER AND LICENSING OF RESULTS

Article 38 — PROMOTING THE ACTION — VISIBILITY OF EU FUNDING

The DeDNAed PDER is part of Task 8.1 on “Dissemination strategy & implementation” led by BNN and Task 8.2 on “Exploitation strategy” led by TECNALIA. The aim of these two tasks is to plan, monitor and implement the project’s communication and dissemination strategy as well as the elaboration of the exploitation strategy. The PDER summarizes the strategy and concrete actions that the DeDNAed Consortium will follow in order to communicate, disseminate and exploit the project results, aiming to help maximize the impact of the project. The communication plan is integrated in the PDER to increase the reciprocal impacts.

Project background and objectives

Note: A full project summary can be found in the original deliverable and was omitted here in the interest of space.

The hypothesis of this project:

The precise localization of bioRE functionalized with ACs in a precisely aligned nanoarray consisting of min. three NPs on a DNA origami provides the basis for a biosensor platform based on SERS detection, which can selectively detect analytes from a solution without major time delays. This system can be further improved by a large-area arrangement of several biosensor units of the same orientation to structures similar to meta-surfaces, which leads to a signal multiplication. This system can be individually adapted through the integrated bioRE, which is validated by various proof-of-concepts with 4 different model analytes critical for current research and the implementation on both solid and flexible, textile substrates. This innovative sensor concept is the basis for **fast, highly sensitive, selective, individually adaptable and low-device biosensors**, which will set **new paradigms in point-of-need (PoN) diagnostics**, such as **food analysis** (aflatoxin) or **medical in-vitro diagnostics** (interleukin-6).

This results in the following **objectives**:

- (1) Establishment of DNA origami as “nano breadboard” for recognition elements.
- (2) Proof of signal enhancement through spatial alignment of recognition elements.
- (3) Demonstration of detection of food containments and bio markers on novel sensor platform.
- (4) Transfer of the sensor platform to a flexible substrate.

Objectives of the first Plan for the Dissemination and Exploitation of Results (PDER)

The aim of this PDER is to bring the project’s aims and objectives to the attention of targeted stakeholders, thus maximizing the potential of the project results beyond its lifetime.

The objectives of the PDER are therefore to:

- **Raise public awareness about the project**, its expected outcomes within defined target groups, using effective communication means and tools;
- **Disseminate for understanding**: Inform the audiences that potentially benefit from the project outcomes.
- **Disseminate to maximize knowledge diffusion** across Europe and internationally;
- **Exchange experience** with related projects and groups working in the field to capture synergies, minimize duplication of work and maximize collaboration potential;
- **Disseminate for action to those groups that can influence and bring about change in their organisations**. Target groups include the R&D industry, SMEs, NGOs, consumers, regulatory and policy agencies, insurers, etc.;
- **Disseminate for marketing**, to bring project outcomes to the marketplace. Target groups here are industrial end users;

- **Ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications** relating to the project results;
- **Utilization of project results in further research activities** other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardization activities.

2. Communication and Dissemination activities

Effectiveness in reaching the target audiences and the impact of the communication and dissemination activities will be assessed on a regular basis as the project progresses, e.g. in (bi)-monthly WP8 meetings. To achieve the full potential of the project, a focus on the individual communication requirements of various audiences associated with the project will be maintained. DeDNAed project Communication and Dissemination Strategy are presented below followed by the developed tools and performed communication activities during the first year of the project.

Communication & Dissemination Strategy

Internal Communication

Overall Project Cooperation

DeDNAed success depends on an open and clear communication between all participants ensuring each participant is kept up-to-date on work progress, next steps, outcomes of meetings and task allocation. DeDNAed partners identified relevant stakeholders. These are divided into internal and external target groups, described in the following subsections.

Consortium partners

The DeDNAed Consortium consists of 7 international partners spreads across 4 countries: Austria, France, Germany and Spain. Internal communication is important for information sharing and to keep motivation high around project Consortium members. This ensures successful dissemination and exploitation of research outcomes and engagement in spreading the project results. It is an extremely important element for delivering the goals of DeDNAed. WP leaders are encouraged to communicate regularly with their co-task participants and to organise discussion meetings concerning task progress, planning and implementation, and development of joint documentation, including input into periodic reports and deliverables. *Monthly project status meetings improve the cooperation between WPs and partners and new results can be easily communicated an/or identified.* For the project management team, communication with the Consortium is on an *ad hoc* basis, as required, and is more formal via regular project meetings that provide updates on overall project progress. Internal communication management is described in Deliverable 1.2. Project Quality Plan under Section 8.

External Communication & Dissemination

All DeDNAed partners will communicate and disseminate relevant project results to the relevant audiences by appropriate means unless there are unresolved issues with intellectual property rights (IPR). WP8 manages all communication and dissemination efforts, and has an obligation to protect IPR

of project outcomes. Each project partner aspires to use open access for all peer-reviewed scientific publications describing their results in line. To develop an efficient Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy for the project and create successful and targeted action plans, we begin by describing the concepts of and differences between communication and dissemination, summarized in Figure 1 and Table 1.

Figure 1. Concept of Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

Table 1. Concepts of Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation.¹

	Communication	Dissemination	Exploitation
Definition ²	Communication on projects is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences , including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.	The public disclosure of project results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including scientific publications, videos and any other medium.	The utilization of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardization activities .
Objectives	Reach out to society and show the impact and benefits of EU-funded R&I activities, e.g., by	Transfer knowledge & results with the aim to enable others to use and take up	Effectively use project results through scientific, economic, political

¹ <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/3bb7278e-ebf3-11e9-9c4e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

² EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary, Reference Terms. <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/glossary>

	addressing and providing possible solutions to fundamental societal challenges.	results, thus maximizing the impact of EU-funded research. Covers project results only .	or societal exploitation routes aiming to turn R&I actions into concrete value and impact for society.
When	Starts at the outset of the project .	Happens only once results are available.	Happens only once results, services or products are available.
Focus	Inform about and promote the project AND its results/success → Focus on the whole project (including results).	Describe and ensure results available for others to use → Focus on results only .	Make concrete use of research results (not restricted to commercial use)
Target Audience	Multiple audiences beyond the project's own community, including the media and general public. Multiplier effect.	Specialist audiences - Groups that may use the results in their own work, including peer groups, industry, professional organisations, policy-makers.	People/organizations including project partners themselves that make concrete use of the project results, as well as user groups outside the project.
Formal Obligations	Legal reference GA Article 38.1	Legal reference GA Article 29	Legal reference GA Article 28

Key Performance Indicators

Table 2 summarizes the planned communication and dissemination activities of the project, including measure and target. All actions have been allocated to communication media and provided with appropriate resources (time and money). The impact of these activities are measured by Key Performance Indicators (KPI) which may lead to a re-planning of the strategy followed. *The KPIs will be evaluated in the technical report.*

Table 2. Planned communication and dissemination activities.

Communication & Dissemination tools	Target audience	Objective	Measure/Target (KPI)	Expected Impact
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Logo and Graphic charter DeDNAed Brand guidelines	All	Create a visual identity of the project	# documents with project brand	Raise awareness of the DeDNAed project
Project Website DeDNAed web-site launching	Public	Core of external communication & dissemination activities to all (public) stakeholders; Provides easy access to project information.	# website hits, page views, clicks # document views	Raise awareness of the DeDNAed project, provide and promote project information and its scope.
C&D Toolkit Project roll-up, flyer(s), slides, deliverable templates, general poster, etc.	Public	Provide online and/or printed project information for dissemination activities such as conferences, meetings and science hotspots.	# items in toolkit # downloaded copies # distributed copies	Raise awareness, engage the general public and scientific community and partners, and promote the project and EU funding.
Social Media (Twitter & LinkedIn accounts and Updates)	Public	General awareness of Project activities and partner efforts. Community building. Addressing defined international target groups via Twitter and LinkedIn.	Accounts activated with 2-3 posts/month, resulting in: # of followers # of postings # of impressions	Attract interest of industry and connect with stakeholders' pages and accounts in social media.
Press Releases	All	Professionally compiled information about the project/results for distribution in (partner's) newsletters and basis for science journalists.	# of Press releases # of articles published from press release	Raise awareness of the DeDNAed project, provide and promote project information and its scope.
Scientific Journals	Scientific Community & industrial parties	Add scientific credibility to results by publishing in peer reviewed journals	# high impact publications (IF) # of citations # Open Access publications	Raise awareness, inform and promote the results obtained to the scientific community, partners and industry.
Research data repository	Scientific Community & industrial parties	Publish in open research data repository platforms such as Zenodo.org.	# Open research documents shared # Linked communities	Open research data to make it possible for third parties to access, print, exploit, reproduce and disseminate data — via a research data repository.
Scientific Conferences	Scientific Community & industrial parties	Dissemination of scientific results	# scientific conferences #oral presentations, posters	Liaison with stakeholders and Present DeDNAed

Conferences, fairs and Exhibitions	Industrial parties, general public	Establish connection with relevant stakeholders , Engaging in direct, face-to-face communications choosing stakeholder-related events.	# conferences, fairs and exhibitions # presentations, posters, articles in newsletters, web/blog	Liaison with stakeholders and Present DeDNAed
Project Workshops, trainings (organization and participation)	Policy makers, Industrial parties & Scientific community	Encourage cross-disciplinary interaction and troubleshooting of project developments	# Project Workshops (scientific, non-scientific)	Liaison with stakeholders and Present DeDNAed
Platforms, Clusters and Associations (news, newsletters, presentations...)	Policy makers, Industrial parties & Scientific community	Establish connections with clusters, platforms and Associations.	# Project presentations as news in webpage, newsletters, oral presentations	Liaison with stakeholders and Present DeDNAed
Internal Workshops, Knowledge Transfer & Training Activities	Internal webinars for ensuring awareness and internal knowledge transfer.	Internal webinars for ensuring awareness and internal knowledge transfer.	# of webinars/trainings # of training materials & recordings produced # of participants Evaluation of feedback of participants	Liaison with stakeholders and Present DeDNAed

Communication and Dissemination activities during the first year

Project Logo

All materials used for the dissemination and communication activities reflect a common visual identity, which is associated with the very first visual identity materials developed, i.e. the project logo. As a first step of the project branding, a project logo and icon were designed (see Figures 2-5). The DeDNAed logo is a combination of the project acronym and a DEDNAED icon, which consists of an origami face mask. This logo can be used with the corporate design colors as well as monochrome in black or white.

Figure 2. DeDNAed logo.

Figure 3. DeDNAed logo black.

Figure 4. DeDNAed logo white.

Figure 5. DeDNAed icon.

Project Website

All information regarding the project website, accessible at <https://dednaed.eu/>, is presented in detail in Deliverable 8.1. “Public project website online” submitted in Month 2. The project website was launched in July 2021, i.e., month 5 of the project runtime.

The following actions were carried out in order to construct the project’s website, in close cooperation by Technische Universität Chemnitz and BioNanoNet Forschungsgesellschaft mbH:

- Purchase of domain (dednaed.eu)
- Purchase of webhosting and SSL certificate
- Selection and purchase of a website template
- Creation and implementation of the project’s email address: info@dednaed.eu
- ‘Coming soon’ website online, including funding acknowledgement and contact information
- Selection of images to be implemented in the website
- Creation and implementation of the website structure:
 - a. **Home**
 - b. **Project**
 - Project summary
 - Objectives
 - Work plan
 - c. **Consortium**
 - Map and logos of the project partners. Description of all partners’ main tasks and contact information.
 - d. **News and media**
 - Latest news and information. Tags: Events, News, Project outcomes
 - e. **Publications**
 - Page to be updated for publications during the project.
 - Public Deliverables, Conference proceedings or references for journal papers
 -

f. Contact

- Contact form that sends all requests to info@dednaed.eu

g. Footer

- Funding acknowledgement
- Link to social media (Twitter & LinkedIn)
- Latest tweets
- Contact information
- Privacy policy
- Legal notice

Project Brand Guideline

To create a recognizable project brand and a coherent image when communicating, a brand guideline for the project has been implemented, which shows how to use the DeDNAEd brand and its components such as fonts, colours and images. [It was presented in Annex 1 of the original deliverable, D8.3.](#)

Communication Toolkit & Dissemination Package

The DeDNAEd “Communication & Dissemination Toolkit” is a collection of materials (created by project partner BNN, in conjunction with the project coordinator) that focus on results and outputs over the course of the project.

This material is and will be used to support communication and dissemination activities. The DeDNAEd “Communication Toolkit” compiles a set of templates that are used by all project partners for internal and external communication purposes (i.e., (i) presentation slides, (ii) meeting minutes, (iii) agenda, and (iv) Deliverable report) and are presented in [Annex 2 of the original deliverable, D8.3.](#)

All communication and dissemination activities developed by every partner in DeDNAEd will be properly registered through the templates that have been prepared for this purpose.

All presentations or other outputs and publications will have the following standard text included at the bottom (or in the acknowledgements for publications):

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research & innovation programme under grant agreement No 964248.

WP8 leader BNN will identify the need for further templates (e.g., for posters, fact sheets, leaflets, etc.) and develop them on demand.

Potential further dissemination materials, created in English, are presented in detail in the next subsections.

Internal templates

[A series of templates were created for the following needs: a Word template for Deliverables and PowerPoint templates for presentations \(internal and external\) and monthly Work Package meetings.](#)

Banner/Roll-up

A project roll-up has been created to provide an additional aid to communication and dissemination activities. It contains very basic information about the project.

The banner is visually oriented and its main purpose will be to gain audience attention and invite them to visit the project website. Its content will be very basic so as to be clear and easily understandable by the target end users.

Flyer

A project flyer has been produced to inform about the DeDNAed project objectives and expected results. It is used for online communication and dissemination (as a PDF). In summer 2022, as conferences and events were increasingly held in person, the flyer was printed and distributed to all consortium members to hand out to the different stakeholder networks at events they attend and organize. The level of detail is generic enough to be used throughout the lifetime of the project and to be understood by most of the stakeholders’ network groups.

General Poster

In light of the still ongoing COVID-19-related travelling restrictions a general project poster has been postponed for now. We will revisit this issue regularly and generate this poster, if needed.

Stickers

In July 2022, stickers with the DeDNAed logo, tag phrase and QR code were ordered and distributed to all project partners to hand out at events and stick at appropriate locations on their campuses.

Social Media in the Project

DeDNAed created its social media accounts in June 2021. Social media will help to reach a wide, but targeted audience, maximizing impact and successful dissemination of the DeDNAed results. The project will continuously post content about project relevant issues. In WP8, content generation will be coordinated by requesting all project beneficiaries to provide content.

Table 3 summarizes the characteristics of the two popular social media networks that have been used by the project, Twitter³ & LinkedIn⁴. The posts provide updates on DeDNAed news, events and any information useful for project. The main aim of using social media is to increase and retain the interest of multiple audiences and to engage new ones. Twitter and LinkedIn are also used to amplify the content generated in the project webpage. To encourage all partners to share social media content, there are reminders at all meetings of WP8.

Table 3. Overview of the characteristics of the two social media platforms used in the project.

Platform	Description – What is it and how can it be used?
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³ https://twitter.com/DeDNAed_project

⁴ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/dednaed/>

<p>Twitter</p>	<p>Twitter is a public forum where anyone can write and share short messages called 'Tweets'. Twitter members can broadcast tweets and follow other users to receive their tweets.</p> <p>280-character messages including links (a URL is always altered to 23 characters). This excludes media attachments (photos, images, videos, etc.) and quoted tweets (displaying someone else`s tweet within your own).</p> <p>Sharing short comments, announcements that can instantaneously reach a large audience or retweeting relevant content.</p>
<p>LinkedIn</p>	<p>LinkedIn is the world's largest professional network on the internet. It can be used to find the right job or internship, connect and strengthen professional relationships. LinkedIn can be accessed from a desktop, LinkedIn mobile app, mobile web experience, or the LinkedIn Lite Android mobile app.</p> <p>A complete LinkedIn profile can help to connect with opportunities by showcasing the project`s unique professional story through experience, skills, and education.</p> <p>Also, LinkedIn can be used to organize offline events, join groups, write articles, post photos and videos, and more.</p>

However, in December 2022-January 2023 it was decided by the consortium to stop using Twitter for the DeDNAed project communication and dissemination. The reasons were twofold: first, due to the unease among consortium members regarding the management of Twitter and fears of disruption of Twitter service or hacking. Second, since many more beneficiaries are present on LinkedIn than on Twitter, LinkedIn has proven a far more effective means of communication and dissemination for the project. We assume that most of the Twitter followers are also following us on LinkedIn. In accordance with current recommendations in the internet safety community, we will maintain the DeDNAed project account on Twitter but, as of January 2023, will no longer post on the platform.

The targeted **social media audience**, i.e., those who follow and who to invite others to follow the DeDNAed profiles, are people who are likely to be interested in the project. We identified three main types of audience: (i) lay people (no special expert knowledge, i.e., general public); (ii) managerial people (may have more knowledge than the lay audience about the subject); (iii) experts (most demanding audience in terms of knowledge); DeDNAed target audiences are (i) the scientific community, (ii) large industry, SMEs and innovators, (iii) state agencies, regulators, policy makers, and (iv) the general public, civil society organisations and media. The postings are tailored to the specific target group by using relevant hashtags and appropriate wording.

The social media **strategy** aims to:

- Identify and engage people and organizations active in fields related to project activities;
- Increase recognition of the project through social media;
- Spread news and other content about the project such as research articles, public deliverables, marketing material, project content, activities, news, results, etc.;
- Engage social media followers; and

- Create interactive forums at an international level.

The project will communicate continuously throughout its lifetime by:

- Launching posts;
- Releasing news items that feature DeDNAed research;
- Linking to any newsletter articles / blog posts DeDNAed produced;
- Promoting conferences DeDNAed will be represented at (interesting oral talks, posters, discussions, etc.);
- Inviting followers for dedicated feedback;
- Publishing interesting news items within the scope of the project;
- Publishing interesting images related to the project topics;
- Reporting new publications or resources produced by the project;
- Replying to relevant tweets by other people;
- Retweeting relevant tweets of other people, projects and organizations;
- Conducting mini-surveys on topics related to the DeDNAed (e.g., users have to vote via choosing an answer or by clicking on 'like', 'applause' or 'heart', etc.);
- Promoting project partner organisations and their staff;
- Presenting WPs and their progress;
- Posting partners' testimonials;
- Any other useful information.

The following is a summary of the different types of social media posts created by BNN for the DeDNAed social media accounts.

Table 4. Types of social media posts, M4-M22

Project Runtime	Description of Activity	Type of Post
M04	Set of Social Media Accounts	
M04	"We have launched" posting	Project news
M05	DeDNAed @ BNN Newsletter	Non-scientific publication
M05	"Let's get social" posting	Project news
M05	Launching of Project Website	Project news
M06	Partner Overview	Partner post
M06	Partner 1	Partner post
M07	SSbD presentation at GIS2021	Event
M07	Partner 2	Partner post
M07	Partner 3	Partner post
M07	Partner 4	Partner post
M07	2. GA today	Event
M08	Partner 5	Partner post
M08	Partner 6	Partner post
M08	Partner 7	Partner post
M08	Project Summary #1	Background
M09	Project Summary #2	Background
M09	Project Summary #3	Background

M09	Project Summary #4	Background
M09	Question: Do you know what kind of platform DeDNAed project is developing?	Background
M10	Objectives	Background
M10	Announcement of WP presentations	Background
M10	Happy Holidays	
M11	WP1	Background
M11	Project Flyer	Project news
M11	New Scientific Director of the @CICbio-maGUNE Center	Partner / Project news
M11	WP8 meeting	Background
M12	WP2 & WP3	Background
M13	WP4	Background
M13	WP5 & WP7	Background
M13	WP6	Background
M14	Poster presentation CIC Blomagune	Event
M14	Announcement of 3rd GA meeting in San Sebastian on 28th, 29th April.	Event
M14	Consortium photo and wrapup	Event
M15	Aitziber L. Cortajarena TedX talk May 7	Event
M15	Royal Spanish Society award	Partner news
M16	BMT	Event
M16	Aicha Azziz poster	Event
M16	Retweet 5000 most cited women CSIC	Partner news
M16	Retweet TEDxAlcoi Aitziber	Partner news
M16	Retweet Saloni A. workshop	Event
M16	DeDNAed @ BNN Quarterly	Non-scientific publication
M17	BMT2022	Event
M17	WP8	
M18	Publication - Julia DNA Origami	Publication
M19	Press conference MAIN	Event
M19	BMT poster & booth	Event
M20	BNN QUARTERLY sign up reminder	Partner news
M20	ERN video	Event
M20	Retweet Saloni molecular interactions	Event
M20	DeDNAed 4th GA video	Event
M20	Repost Saloni UP Science Day	Event
M20	Nerea BMT poster content	Event
M20	Dednaed @ Quarterly	Non-scientific publication
M21	Mathis Janßen Poster MAIN General Assembly	Event
M21	TUC lab video	Project video
M21	Repost Aicha presentation	Event
M21	Repost BNN 12DaysNanomaterials	Partner news
M21	Happy Holidays	Project news

DeDNAed Stakeholders

DeDNAed target audiences and general stakeholder groups are (i) large industry/SMEs/innovators, (ii) the scientific community, (iii) state agencies/regulators/policy makers, and (iv) the general public, civil society organisations and media. DeDNAed consortium plans also to disseminate results within clusters and stakeholders. This is complemented by the organization and attendance of workshops and partnering days for the different clusters & networks. The clusters that are considered and a responsible contact person in DeDNAed consortium are listed in Table 5. The contact partner is to be present in cluster/network events, and chooses how to reach to the cluster/network. All stakeholder engagement activities will be performed GDPR compliant.

Table 5. Stakeholder and Clusters.

Stakeholder	Regional, national, european	Contact person
EU NanoSafety Cluster https://www.nanosafetycluster.eu/nsc-overview/nsc-structure/coordination-team/	European Cluster	BNN, Andreas Falk (Ceo) – Coordination
Nanomedicine Austria https://www.bionanonet.at/support/alliances-clustering/nanomedicine-austria/	National platform, Austria	BNN, Susanne Resch, National platform <i>Coordinator</i>
Photonics Austria https://www.photonics-austria.at/en/home-english/	National Platform, Austria	BNN, Andreas Falk (CEO), member
BNN Association https://www.bnn.at/association/structure/	International Association, <i>The BNN mbH counts with the BioNanoNet association that compiles currently 66 international members (research centres, universities and industry).</i>	BNN, Andreas Falk (CEO)
Biosaxony https://www.biosaxony.com/en/about-us	National Cluster, (Dresden, Germany)	KSI-Meinsberg, Andreas Heerwig
DECHEMA https://dechema.de/en/	National expert Network for chemical engineering and biotechnology (Frankfurt am Main, Germany)	KSI-Meinsberg, Andreas Heerwig
Forschungsgemeinschaft Technik und Glas e.V http://f-t-g.org/	Research association for technology and glass, as a non-profit sponsoring association (Bronnbach, Germany)	KSI-Meinsberg, Andreas Heerwig
Arbeitskreis Mikrosystemtechnik für die Biotechnologie http://www.biomst.eu/index_d.html	National network	KSI-Meinsberg, Andreas Heerwig
AMA Verband für Sensorik und Messtechnik e.V. https://www.ama-sensorik.de/	Network for the key sector of sensor and measurement technology.	KSI-Meinsberg, Andreas Heerwig
Healthy Saxony	National Communication platform for the promotion of (cross-	Technical University Chemnitz, Andreas Moschhauser

https://www.healthy-saxony.com/	network) cooperation in the health care industry in Saxony, Germany	
IVAM e.V. https://www.ivam.de/	Professional association for micro-technology, Germany	Technical University Chemnitz, Andreas Moschhauser
Silicon Saxony https://www.silicon-saxony.de/home/	Microelectronics and IT cluster, Germany and Europe	Technical University Chemnitz, Danny Reuter
Europäische Forschungsgesellschaft Dünne Schichten eV - EFDS https://www.efds.org/	National Network in the field of thin-film technology, Germany	Technical University Chemnitz, Danny Reuter

Newsletter: Partner BNN produces and publishes a newsletter four times a year, with an established and growing group of recipients. DeDNAed will be offered to contribute to this useful means of dissemination, by adding project-related news, activities, and results (e.g., recent publications, services, etc) to this newsletter.

Scientific Publications and events

The project results are disseminated to the scientific community by scientific publications in high-tier peer reviewed general and specialized journals (e.g., *Biosensors and Bioelectronics*, *Nanoscale*, *Nanotechnology*, *ACS NANO*, *Langmuir*, *JACS*, *ACS Applied Materials and Interfaces* and others) and conferences (e.g., *European Biosensors Symposium*, *BIOCHIP Berlin* and others) to inform the scientific community about cutting-edge results, stimulate scientific discourse, and raise visibility. Technological parts of the research are published in the relevant industrial journals. The preferred strategy for peer-reviewed open access scientific publication is the **green or gold open access**.

As required by Article 29.1 of the GA, if a beneficiary intends to disseminate results during the project or for a period of 1 year after the end of the project, it must give at least 21 calendar days advance notice to the other beneficiaries and sufficient information on the results that will be disseminated. Objections to publication must be received within 14 days of receiving the notification of intention to disseminate. Further details on how to deal with objections are agreed upon in the CA.

A list of publications, including posters and conference proceedings as well as academic publications, can be found in the EC Portal and in the attached Communications & Dissemination log.

Open Research data

Additionally, Article 29.2 sets out the rules for the open access on digital research data. Beneficiaries of actions participating in the Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP) must give open, free-of-charge access to the end-user to digital **research data** generated during the action. Without compromising the exploitation strategy, results of DeDNAed will be disseminated by the OpenAire platform Zenodo.

Scientific publications and public deliverables of DeDNAed project will be made openly available by the **repository platform Zenodo.org**.

Zenodo supports the sharing, curation and publication of data and software. It assigns all publicly available uploads a DOI to make the data set easily and uniquely citeable. Zenodo supports making the data findable by allowing harvesting of all content via the OAI-PMH protocol; citation information is also passed to DataCite and onto the scholarly aggregators. Furthermore, OpenAIRE integrates into existing reporting lines to the EU Commission, allowing the funding body to be notified when data is shared. Finally, Zenodo allows the creation of collections, which could be used to increase the cross-visibility of data sets created within the DeDNAed project. All these features make it an ideal choice in order to gain the desired visibility and accessibility for DeDNAed data. Peer-reviewed publications will be made available based on journal requirements.

Figure 6. [DeDNAed Zenodo](https://zenodo.org/communities/dednaed/) repository created.

The European Commission has lately launched the Open Research Europe⁵. As an open access publisher, it might be very useful for the project outcomes of DeDNAed. The DeDNAed Consortium will discuss the possibility of using this platform for publication over the coming months.

Conferences, Fairs, non-scientific and Public events

Relevant industrial conferences, exhibitions and fairs such as [BioChip Berlin](#), [NALS](#), [BMT](#), [Medica](#), [EuroNanoForum](#), [Clinam](#) and [MedFit](#) will be of interest of the DeDNAed partners to make the research visible and raise awareness of key industrial actors in the project technological field.

Public events for promotion of tailored events for young researchers and networks. Participation in scientific events to general public (including kids, students, patient foundations...) such as "Science days", "European Researchers Night", "Science week", "World disease day..." will be fostered. Attendance to conference, fairs and participation in events is monitored in the [EIC_DeDNAed_CommDiss_Log](#) (see Annex 1) .

⁵ <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>

Educational activities, synergies, attendance to funding events and others

The university partners take part in activities in their degree programs and will inform and engage students in the field of innovative biosensors. Synergies will be continuously sought with existing and new networks. DeDNAed participants will participate in events that target developing research strategies beyond DeDNAed project. Educational activities, new networks and synergy activities and attendance to funding events and others will be monitored in the EIC_DeDNAed_CommDiss_Log.

Monitoring Communication and Dissemination activities

Although WP8 will coordinate the communication and dissemination activities, all DeDNAed project partners are expected to actively participate in activities. To monitor them, a template “**EIC_DeDNAed_CommDiss_Log.xlsx**” (Annex 1) was created by BNN and shared with all partners on the shared file server. The categories to choose as type of communication and dissemination activity are based on the periodic reporting required in the EC Participants’ Portal.

The following information will be reported by all partners:

- Project runtime (month xx)
- Date/time period (dd.mm.yyyy)
- Partner (Acronym) (lead partner in bold)
- Location
- Communication & Dissemination Activity:
 - Project Meeting
 - Organisation of a conference
 - Organisation of a workshop
 - Press release
 - Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)
 - Exhibition
 - Flyer
 - Training
 - Social media
 - Website
 - Communication campaign (e.g., radio, TV)
 - Participation to a conference
 - Participation to a workshop
 - Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop
 - Video / Film
 - Brokerage event
 - Pitch event
 - Trade fair
 - Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)
 - Other
- Title

- Content, brief description, purpose
- No. of views, attendees and/or prints (add time period)
- Type of audience addressed:
 - Scientific community (higher education, research)
 - Industry
 - Civil society
 - General public
 - Policy makers
 - Media
 - Investors
 - Customers
 - Other
- Related Open Access documents (to be potentially shared at e.g., project website)
- External link to activity (if relevant)
- Link to event at project webpage
- Project internal/external activity
- Comments

A different template is used to monitor the publications specifically, also based on the form at the EC Participants' Portal:

- Type (select from dropdown list)
- Title
- Author(s)
- Title of Journal/Proceedings/Books series/Book (for book chapters)
- Year
- Page reference
- DOI
- Repository link
- Open Access Status (Green/Gold)
- Date to release on project website
- Comments

Activities are planned to engage with relevant stakeholders. If possible, these activities will be potentially merged with sister projects' activities or conferences to better interact with the relevant stakeholders and to join efforts with other ongoing activities, reaching a wider community, thus saving and aligning resources. The communication and dissemination activities will be updated regularly and compiled within the regular PDER updates at M36.

All communication and dissemination activities comply with the GDPR rules and are aligned with the privacy policy of the project. All relevant-for-the-community communication and dissemination activities will be reported on the website and/or social media channels of the project.

Completed Communication & Dissemination Activities

Main DeDNAed activities (dissemination material, events, workshops, newsletters, etc.) are announced in the “News & Media” section of the project website as well as in the social media channels of the project (LinkedIn & formerly Twitter). Furthermore, all activities by all partners are compiled and regularly updated in the list “DeDNAed_Communication&Dissemination_Log.xlsx” (Annex 1).

3. Exploitation plan

This document describes the initial Exploitation Plan customized for the DeDNAed project. The Exploitation Plan will be periodically updated throughout the project lifetime, with the final version (D8.7) due month 36. The partners in DeDNAed project must, in accordance with the article 28.1 in GA, take necessary measures to ensure the exploitation of the project results up to 4 years after the end of the project.

The Exploitation Plan aims to cover the most important topics concerning how the project results that will be generated during the project lifetime could be exploited, including exploitation results identification by each of the partners in the consortium, types of exploitation, and the most suitable platforms for each type of exploitation.

The second version of the exploitation plan includes a new exploitable result identified in last 12 months and an update of the exploitable results reported in month 12. Future versions of exploitation plan will be reported at month 36.

Innovation objectives of DeDNAed project

Combination of the advantages of SERS and DNA origami can be applied to new generation of biosensors, creating highly ordered 2D arrays from at least three NPs in order to create hot spots of defined quantities and local distribution in the light-exposed areas. In this way, the positioning of the bioRE in the light-exposed hotspots of the NPs enables the respective analyte to be detected qualitatively and quantitatively directly from a supernatant solution. The heterogeneous functionalization consisting of a highly ordered SERS array and an individually adaptable bioRE as a biosensor has not yet been described in the literature and offers great innovation potential due to increased selectivity, sensitivity and speed.

DeDNAed is therefore trying to answer those challenges and set its main innovation objectives as:

- Using the variability of the DNA origami as a binding matrix for various bioRE and NP offers the possibility to construct individual structures and arrays and to adapt them to the requirements of the measurement method.
- Integrating several heterogeneous bioRE, the additional function of multivalent binding of a target can be supplemented, so that the selectivity towards foreign bones within the analyte solution can be increased.
- Increasing the applicability of the sensor platform using flexible substrates in addition to solid substrates by means of lipid-bilayers for use in textiles or as wipe test.

The detection of various model analytes with high research relevance such as interleukin-6 (IL-6), aflatoxin, cancer DNA and recombinant surface proteins of influenza is intended to verify the high application potential of the sensor platform in the point-of-care diagnostics.

Next table shows the key exploitable results (KERs) (Table 6). Each WP leader collects the information provided by partners involved in each work package each 12 Months.

Table 6. KERs template

At month 24, 4 KERs are identified:

No.	KER Title	Short description/ Application	Partners (leader and contribution)	Type	TRL and additional research required	IPR
1	Cluster decorated, DNA origami compatible DNA based bioRE	Development of DNA oligonucleotide sequences with three sequences with independent functionalities, incorporating semiconductor and metallic clusters under physiological conditions. / Improving biocompatibility and increasing the modularity of the system.	CICB	Synthesis protocol	TRL4, requires further proof of feasibility and proof of concept integration into DNA origami system	Trade secret and patenting will be considered
2	Cluster decorated, DNA origami compatible Antibody based bioRE	Integration of atomic clusters in the structure of an antibody under physiological conditions and maintaining the affinity of the antibody for target analyte. / Improving the sensitivity of the biosensor and the storage time in comparison with traditional labelled antibodies.	TEC and CICB	Synthesis protocol	Actually, TRL3 for the methodology, adaptation of the method for IL6 antibody, for secondary antibody and aflatoxin B1 antibody during the project.	Patented extend to Europe and USA (in progress)
3	DNA origami sensor platform based on SERS detection	bioRE functionalized with ACs in a precisely aligned nano array consisting of min. three NPs on a DNA origami for a detection of analytes by SERS detection./ Improving the sensitivity of the biosensor achieving very low LOD and possibility of analysis	All	Demonstrator	TRL1, development of proof-of-concept prototype.	Patenting will be considered

		from samples with complex matrix				
4	Thin-film system for selective surface immobilisation	Thin-film system of bond-attractive and bond-resistant layer based on SiO ₂ and Parylene and a further surface modification of bond-attractive and bond-resistant area to improve selectivity. Universal platform for the immobilization of the different components of a biosensor with nanometric precision.	TUC and UP	Process protocol	TRL3-4, requires further proof of feasibility and proof of concept integration into DNA origami hybrid, preliminary tests with functionalised DNA origami completed	Protection of design will be considered

The management of the exploitation and the detailed elaboration of the exploitation strategy will be handled by the Innovation and Exploitation manager (IEM), Goran Bijelic from Tecnalía. The main responsibilities of the IEM are: to identify all results with exploitation potential; to define best manner to manage intellectual property; and to find exploitation opportunities for DeDNAed solutions.

The exploitation plan structure is composed by four sections:

- A. Exploitable innovations and ambitions
- B. Objective of exploitation
- C. Exploitation strategy
- D. IPR management

Next, each section is going to be described and elaborated for each KER individually. The information is collected from the consortium partners, and the contents may evolve throughout the project lifetime along with the development of the KER.

A. Exploitable innovations and ambitions

This section describes the novelty value of the innovations generated in the project as well as their advantages and disadvantages compared to existing similar technologies or products in the industry and market.

KER 1. Cluster decorated, DNA origami compatible DNA based bioRE

Development of DNA oligonucleotide sequences with three sequences with independent functionalities, incorporating semi-conductor and metallic clusters under physiological conditions. The three functional segments are: 1) The DNA sequence complementary to corresponding sequence in DNA origami for attachment to the latter; 2) The sequence which is able to stabilize formation of semiconductor /or metallic atomic clusters, functioning as a specific marker eg. for optical analysis; 3) The sequence of DNA probe/DNA aptamer for specific binding with the target analyte. This methodology

is being tested for the detection of aflatoxin, as one of the most carcinogenic substances produced by plant-infesting mold.

Innovation properties and benefits: the novelty of this system lies in the incorporation of three functional segments in one bio-compatible platform based on single-stranded DNA. This benefits the ease of the synthesis, which in turn increases biocompatibility by avoiding further, potentially denaturing, reactions. Furthermore, does the use of three functional groups increase the modularity of the system, with each functional group being independently adjustable to fit and adjust the needs of the overall system.

Limitations: the system is mainly limited by the need to avoid cross-functionalities between the three elements, meaning that the specific functionality of one element imposes restrictions on the design of the other two and vice versa. These limitations can be addressed in the design stage, but each specific system interaction needs to be tested for the occurrence of eventually unpredicted interactions or inhibitions between the three parts.

The ambition and future actions in exploitation of KER 1 should follow development and validation of several named applications including corresponding functional prototypes. IP protection allows dissemination and promotion in research publications and targeted fairs and conferences presentations and publications. In addition, core partners responsible for development and protection of IP, should promote the developed exploitation assets within research community as primary market where additional customized and further developed applications could be offered as R&D service without IPR transfer. In second stage of commercialization, after consideration of manufacturability and scale up, we should target focal industrial sectors in biotechnology and biosensing should be addressed through channels described in Exploitation strategy, where licensing of KER 1 technology and even creation of a start up company could be considered.

[KER 2. Cluster decorated, DNA origami compatible Antibody based bioRE](#)

This KER consists on the synthesis of semiconductor and metallic clusters using an antibody as scaffold under non-denaturing conditions. The secondary structure of the antibody does not suffer any alteration during the synthesis and therefore the antibody maintains its binding ability for antigen. The antibody carrying atomic clusters can be used in immunoassays acting as a probe, incorporating the biorecognition element and the transducer.

Nanoclusters (NCs) have attained great attention in the last few years due to their size dependent optical and chemical properties. Nowadays, a large number of methods using proteins as scaffold have been developed for NCs synthesis. Usually, the synthetic conditions for the synthesis of NCs stabilized with proteins require extreme conditions of pH or temperature. These conditions cause the denaturalization of the proteins and end up in the loss of their biological functions. The innovation relies in the physiological conditions used during the synthesis, which do not affect the antibody structure. The resulting antibodies still maintain the affinity for target analyte. Incorporate both a recognition component (to sense selective interaction with the bioanalyte) and a transducer component (to deliver the corresponding interaction).

Innovation properties and benefits: the use of NCs embedded in the antibody structure offer advantages in terms of sensitivity and results in the development of new efficient strategies for the detection system of immunoassays. Traditionally antibodies for immunoassays applications are labelled

with natural enzymes with the inherent disadvantages associated with the use of enzymes, like high susceptibility to environmental variations, easy denaturation and digestion, costly and time-consuming preparation and purification. Moreover, it is needed a crosslinking reaction between the enzyme and the antibody which generate non-desired species by random coupling that causes high background signals due to non-specific absorption. By the introduction of the NCs into the antibody structure this drawback disappears, and the signal-to-noise ratio decreases and thus the sensitivity increases. The use of NCs as antibodies labels also offer advantages in long term storage in comparison with traditional antibodies labels.

Limitations: the methodology is robust when polyclonal antibodies are used as scaffold, the synthetic route has been applied in various polyclonal antibodies with a positive result. However, when monoclonal antibodies are used, they get denaturalised during the synthesis and also, they loss their biological functions and thus, the affinity for target analyte suffers a huge decrease and practically disappear.

Exploitation of KER 2 should, depending on results to be further obtained and success in IP protection, should follow the ambition similar to KER 1. It may be of particular interest at later stage of the project with more evidence of system performance to consider exploitation synergies and joined commercialization steps for KER 1 and KER 2.

KER 3. DNA origami sensor platform based on SERS detection

DNA origami sensor platform based on SERS detection is based on the precise localization of bioRE functionalized with ACs in a precisely aligned nano array consisting of minimum three NPs on a DNA origami. This innovative sensor concept is the basis for fast, highly sensitive, selective, individually adaptable and low-device biosensors, which will set new paradigms in point-of-need (PoN) diagnostics, such as food analysis (aflatoxin) or medical in-vitro diagnostics (interleukin-6).

Innovation properties and benefits: the presented sensor principle can open up solutions with the fast and highly sensitive measurement method due to the combination of the high selective biological recognition elements and the fast optical measurement method of the SERS (10-30 s) with very low-limit of detection (10 pM). The sensor system does not require a sample preparation but analyses the analyte directly from the complex sample with little equipment.

The limitation will be defined in larger stage of the project.

Upon the decision regarding model of IP protection and when patent-design-know how document is filed, KER 3 could be considered as good candidate for pre-commercialization steps related to real life benchmarking with similar products present on the market where competitive advantages over SOA may be confirmed and further promoted in the sector of diagnostics and PON oriented industry. Like in case of KER 1 and KER 2 synergic exploitation steps and presentation of the exploitable assets to same target group of investors-clients can be considered.

KER 4. Optimized thin-film system for selective surface immobilisation

This KER consists on the development of a thin-film system compatible with the designed DNA origami template structure. Then the DNA-origami first and the DNA-origami hybrid later will be immobilised in the substrates employing both physisorption and chemisorption. For this the DNA-origami will be synthesised introducing in its structure modifications like different functional groups.

Innovation properties and benefits: the integration of the DNA origami into a substrate and the development of a thin film is the first step beyond the development of a PoC biosensor platform. The versatility of functionalization of DNA origami due to DNA complementary single strands interactions provides a universal platform for the immobilization of the different components of a biosensor (biorecognition element, transduction element...). After PoC is developed this thin film system will provide a bioengineered surface to target group of users-clients in research community from the field with 2 aims promoting technology, further developing the application scope, attracting attention of various industrial sectors Health and Agri-food primarily.

Limitation: the introduction of some functional groups into the DNA origami structure for its further immobilisation in the proposed substrates can affect to the functionality of the DNA origami hybrid. This limitation will be defined in larger stage of the project.

KER 4 as anticipated shows great capacity for exploitation through customised development of sensing surfaces for immobilization of various bio-sensing entities depending on specific application and client need, that can be offered as advanced R&D service and where properties over protected design can be transferred to specific client. By nature, price and level of protection we may consider a family of designs related to various application developed with project that could serve evidence and illustration of technology and its applicability as well as potential exploitable result in case of transfer-mon- etization.

B. Objective of exploitation

In case of exploitation route oriented to research community in the field identified as primary access to market, scientific impact of KERs will be based on providing novel technology developed and validated in the Project to various research groups where in collaborative work or independently further research and scientifically relevant findings may arise. At the same time, as the KERs are offering advanced and novel research and development methods, they are great platform for education in particular for PhD programs or specialization courses for bio-engineers. Approaches we have considered in exploitation, are primarily oriented to support further development of the KERs as they are translational results still far from the marketable product or service, so the first economic impact is related to obtaining funding for second cycle of R&D that should result with development of Industrial prototype and involve principal exploitation stakeholders preferably from EU industrial sector. Societal impact apart from the education and economic growth based on innovative technology, is primarily oriented to improved Health and Quality of life of the EU citizens where new, green, low cost and high-performance technology for various biosensing applications will be one step closer to become part of our daily life.

KER 1. Cluster decorated, DNA origami compatible DNA based bioRE

Scientifically, the cluster decorated, DNA origami compatible DNA based bioRE is expected to generate knowledge on labelling of BioRE and a usefulness like a biosensing elements, superior than current state-of-the-art. Economically, CICB contemplates monetizing the results through license.

KER 2. Cluster decorated, DNA origami compatible Antibody based bioRE

Scientifically, the cluster decorated, DNA origami compatible Antibody based bioRE is expected to generate knowledge on labelling of BioRE and a usefulness like a biosensing elements for immunoassays, superior to current state-of-the-art. Economically, CICB and TEC contemplates monetizing the results through license (process already patented).

KER 3. DNA origami sensor platform based on SERS detection

Scientifically, the exploitation aims to show a new sensing platform for SERS detection based on DNA origami with BioRe elements decorated with clusters. During the project two specific uses cases will be targeted in order to show the performance of this platform, detection of IL-6 and detection of aflatoxin B1 (AF-B1). For the society, this sensing platform creates the possibility to provide a new point of care (PoC) device with advanced features, which can be further used to detect different analytes. Lastly, for the commercial viewpoint, the partners are expected to monetize the result.

The objectives of the exploitation are to further strengthen partners' organization competitiveness in the research community and in the market via the increased know-how in DNA origami sensor platform based on SERS detection, synthesis of related components, process conditions, issues, and market insights as well as to gain financial reward from the new product commercialization through licensing or cooperation agreements.

KER 4. Optimized thin-film system for selective surface immobilisation

The exploitation aims to show a strategy to developed thin-film systems for surface immobilization of DNA-origami hybrids. For the society, the development of this hybrid structure creates the possibility to provide a ultra-sensible system that can be used as a universal biosensing platform to PoC biosensing. Allowing to detect analytes that has not been possible until for low concentration in complexes matrix.

The economic objective will be further elaborated in future versions of the Exploitation Plan.

C. Exploitation strategy

In the last five years, the total invested in seed and Series A fundraisings of biotech companies has doubled to reach over €3Bn per year. A particularly big difference can be seen within the European biotech ecosystem. Our primary exploitation focus will be oriented towards EU based entities in final stages of commercialization, where in initial steps our strategy will stay open to global funding and technology alliances following the Open Innovation concept described further in this section.

Our exploitation strategy is to contact and connect with open innovation such as J&J's four 'innovation centers' in London, Shanghai, Boston and California, where the company brings together a network of scientists and investors. That is, intermediate step until the technology reaches a more mature stage and is ready for a licensing or acquisition deal. This approach will provide the requisites including funding for all the development stages and help us to disperse the risks as we bring our project results forward and point at what is needed to make a product commercial.

In order to attract the investment, we need to consider how to scale up and what is required in this process. Early in the r&d cycle, where we are now we need to consider one or few core assets and

limited programmes, focusing our resources where the most value can be gained such as differentiation in manufacturing and understanding of final application.

To ensure that our exploitation efforts are driven in right direction we should be working closely with relevant companies and R&D institutions conducting innovative research required to continue the development of pre-clinical assets. This will enable us to demonstrate the strength of our R&D capabilities and pipeline, driving market confidence and the subsequent willingness of other players to collaborate and partner at both IPO and later maturity stages.

Together with the Market analysis (M36) and Business Plan (M36) the exploitation strategy will define the paths how the innovations of the project can be exploited and delivered to the market, during the project lifetime and after the end of the project. The Exploitation strategy will consist of: Target applications, customers or users; Exploitation routes and timeline; and responsibility.

KER 1. Cluster decorated, DNA origami compatible DNA based bioRE

Exploitation routes will be further evaluated at a later stage of the project. At current stage, the involved partners CICB are planning to exploit this KER by using it for further collaborative research or licensing the IP rights. The expected TRL by the end of project will reach level 4. In the long-term, production and commercialization are also under consideration in the case that additional partners will be involved through industrial cooperation agreement(s).

KER 2. Cluster decorated, DNA origami compatible Antibody based bioRE

Exploitation routes will be further evaluated at a later stage of the project. At current stage, potential exploitation routes under considerations include use for further research, develop and sell the new product/service, and license IP rights. The expected TRL by the end of project will reach level 4 for the detection of IL6 through secondary antibody and detection of aflatoxin. In the long-term, production and commercialization are also under consideration in the case that additional partners will be involved through industrial cooperation agreement(s).

KER 3. DNA origami sensor platform based on SERS detection

Exploitation routes will be further evaluated at a later stage of the project. Diagnostic industry and manufacturing of intermediates are considered as the target customers who may be interested in the results.

Numerous potential exploitation routes are under consideration to exploit the DNA origami sensor platform based on SERS detection, including use for further research, develop and sell the new product/service, spin-off activity, cooperation agreement/joint-venture, sell IP rights or IP based business, license IP rights, or transfer ownership of IP rights to another partner from the consortium. The TRL is projected to reach level 4 by the end of the project, thus further developments for optimization of the process condition have to be conducted in order to bring this result to commercial market in 6 to 8 years after the project. At a later stage of the project, the suitable routes will be chosen and further elaborated.

KER 4. Optimized thin-film system for selective surface immobilisation

Exploitation routes will be further evaluated at a later stage of the project. Diagnostic industry and manufacturing of intermediates are considered as the target customers who may be interested in the results. The TRL is projected to reach level 4 by the end of the project.

D. IPR management

The three strategies that are proposed to be followed to protect the intellectual property of the KERs are: Patent, Known-how and Protection of design.

It is essential to have a proper IPR management for partners to effectively exploit the project results without violating the IPR of others. At current stage, it is still too early to provide concrete details about IPR management while the results are still in the process of development. In the future versions of the Exploitation Plan, the need for protection of the KERs generated in the project (IP) will be assessed. Basic rules of the ownership allocation have been set out in the article 26 in the GA, considering that some exploitable results will be generated by more than one partner, the methodology to allocate the IP ownership should be established in fair and reasonable condition based on each partner's contribution towards the foreground IP development in the later stage of the project.

KER 1. Cluster decorated, DNA origami compatible DNA based bioRE

Background IP from CICB are required to develop the cluster decorated, DNA origami compatible DNA based bioRE. CICB has 2 patents in the field and knowledge and practical expertise in the design, synthesis and characterization of cluster decorated DNA based bioRE.

At the current stage, trade secret and patenting are the two potential protections that are under consideration. The scope of IP protection will be further defined in later stage of the project. Cluster decorated, DNA origami compatible DNA based bioRE will be developed by CICB.

KER 2. Cluster decorated, DNA origami compatible Antibody based bioRE

Background IP from CICB and TEC are required to co-develop the cluster decorated, DNA origami compatible antibody based bioRE. CICB and TEC have a specific co-patent where the methodology of the introduction of cluster on antibody is protected, and knowledge and practical expertise in the design, synthesis and characterization of cluster decorated antibody based bioRE.

In February 2022 CICB and TEC decided to extend the patent to the EEUU and on April the application was submitted. The patent process in Europe continues by the request of the European Patent Office from the Patent Cooperation Treaty. The patent is public since August 2022.

KER 3. DNA origami sensor platform based on SERS detection

Several background IP have been brought by multiple partners into DeDNAed project and have been listed in the attachment 1 in the consortium agreement (CA), including background description and access right within the project for implementation. In brief, partners are granted on a royalty-free basis or with fair and reasonable conditions for the background needed to carry out the implementation within the project scope.

At the current stage, trade secret and patenting are the two potential protections that are considered for DNA origami sensor platform based on SERS detection. Ideally the scope of the IP protection shall be global.

KER 4. Optimized thin-film system for selective surface immobilisation

Background IP from TUC and UP are required to develop the thin-film system for selective surface immobilization. At the current stage, protection of the design is the potential protection that is under consideration. The scope of IP protection will be further defined in later stage of the project.

4. Conclusions

This PDER provides DeDNAEd with a solid framework for communicating, disseminating and exploiting project results and activities. The DeDNAEd consortium will use this document as an initial strategy that will be further revised and updated as dissemination materials and specific strategies are evaluated to reach effectiveness in targeting stakeholders and in aligning with stakeholder interests and problems.

The PDER captures and schedules all communication and dissemination activities of the project that support engagement of new stakeholders and increase public awareness of the project and its outcomes. It will assist the project partners by defining communication goals, objectives and strategies by outlining specific dissemination events in which to participate and dissemination activities to perform.

Upcoming updates of the PDER will explain how the project plans to guide the consortium partners through the exploitation process of DeDNAEd results to achieve the expected impacts. In conclusion, the DeDNAEd PDER employs diverse communication channels, ranging from a project website and social media accounts, etc., through to participation in events (conferences, workshops, meetings, events, joint activities with relevant EU projects, etc.) to maximise internal communications and external interactions with stakeholders.

In general, the performance regarding communication and dissemination of results **thus far has been satisfactory**. As soon as new findings and results are available, the measures described in the PDER apply. As leader of WP8, BNN continuously monitors and coordinates future communication and dissemination activities. All project partners will be encouraged to perform further outreach activities and spread the word about the DeDNAEd progress in their communities. The PDER will be updated regularly, with the **last formal update in M36**.

5. References & Bibliography

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Annexes

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DELIVERABLE 8.5

List of Communication & Dissemination activities related to the project, in chronological order.

Project Runtime	Date/Time period (dd.mm.yyyy)	Partner (Acronym) (lead partner in bold)	Location	Comm. & Diss. Activity (select from drop-down list)	Title	Content/Brief description/Purpose	Scientific community (higher education, research)	Number of Attendees								Related Open Access documents	External link to activity (if relevant)	Link to event at project webpage	Countries addressed	Language of activity	Comments		
								Industry	Civil society	General public	Policy makers	Media	Investors	Customers	Other								
M13	22.03.2022	BNN	Online	Participation to a conference	2nd Stakeholder Workshop on Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD), organized by the EC and JRC	The Sustainable Framework was discussed, as well as its relation to the EU Green Deal and the Chemical Strategy for	150	150	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	2nd Safe and Sustainable-by-Design stakeholder workshop - YouTube		All	English		
M14	27-29.04.2022	CICB	Santander	Participation to a conference	NALS Conference: Functional ssDNA for the development of a DNA origami biosensor	Poster presentation												https://nalsconferences.com/		All	English	tbd	
M15	10-11.05.2022	UP	Berlin	Participation to a conference	Biochip Berlin	Visitor																	
M19	28-20.09.2022	BNN	Innsbruck	Organisation of a workshop	Joint Annual Conference of the Austrian, German and Swiss Societies for Biomedical Engineering, BMT 2022	Poster presentation	80	10	0	0	0	2	0	3	0		https://www.bmt2022.at/		All	English			
M19	28-20.09.2022	BNN	Innsbruck	Exhibition	Joint Annual Conference of the Austrian, German and Swiss Societies for Biomedical Engineering, BMT 2022	Booth with C&D toolkit of DeDNAed	80	10	0	0	0	2	0	3	0		https://www.bmt2022.at/		All	English			
M19	19.-23.9.2022	Lamy de la Chapelle)	Rome	Participation to a conference	Nanoinnovation 2022	Marc planning to attend																	
M19	30.09.2023	BNN	St. Poelten (AT)	Exhibition	European Researchers' Night	Booth with C&D toolkit of DeDNAed	45	0	200	200	0	5	0	0	50								
M19	05.09.2022	TUC	Chemnitz	Press release	Assignment of Prof. Schmidt as Scientific Director of the MAIN Institute	Presentation of important projects of MAIN building	10	0	0	50	0	0	0	0	0				Germany	German/English			
M20	13.10.2022	UP	Potsdam	Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop	University of Potsdam Science Day	Poster presented at science day	0	0	0	80	0	0	0	0	0								
M20	10.10.2022	TUC	Chemnitz	Participation to a conference	MAIN General Assembly	Poster presented	20	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	https://www.chemnitz.de/10.5281/zenodo.680373	https://dednaed.eu/dednaed-main-general-assembly/		Germany	English			
M21	25.11.2022	Le Mans (Aicha Aziz)	Paris	Participation to a conference	GDR Plasmonique Active	Oral presentation "Observation of DNA strand conformation with SERS"	50	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0								
M22	23.12.2022	IMMM	Le Mans	Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)	L'Experimentarium: Des Nanoparticules pour Detecter les Cancers	Description of DeDNAed and her life as a scientist	9	0	0	70	0	0	0	0	0		https://www.linkedin.com/posts/aicha-aziz-5b4a96142_dednaed-research-experimentarium-activity-7010919068383772672-190-?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop			French	https://www.linkedin.com/posts/aicha-aziz-5b4a96142_dednaed-research-experimentarium-activity-7010919068383772672-190-		
M24	16-18.02.2023	IMMM (Aicha Aziz)	Lisbon	Participation to a conference	International Congress of Photoptics 2023	2 posters presented	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		https://photoptics.sciteven.ts.org/?y=2023						
M24	16-18.02.2023	IMMM (Marc Lamy de la Chapelle)	Lisbon	Participation to a conference	International Congress of Photoptics 2023	1 oral presentation	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		https://photoptics.sciteven.ts.org/?y=2023						